

Experiments in Uncertainty and Un/knowing: Economics and Visual Arts Perspectives on Climate Change Mitigation

*A workshop co-hosted by [LEAP Lab](#) and [ICENS Lab](#)
23 June 2025, 9.45am-2.30pm, Alison Richard Building, University of Cambridge*

1. What is this event about?

Uncertainty takes many forms, from risks and known probabilities to randomness and incomplete knowledge. It is a fundamental feature of our economies and our world. Its presence is even more pronounced when considering long-term climate change, and the possible intended and unintended consequences of climate action. Conventional economic theory, which informs much decision-making on sustainability issues typically confers negative connotations to risk and uncertainty. Instead, it values certainty, stability, and a known/knowable environment for actors' behaviours (e.g. investment decisions). Uncertainty is either tamed or ignored, but rarely accepted and embraced.

The workshop proposes to unpack, question, reimagine, and befriend uncertainty, moving between the abstract and the concrete, between the seen and the unseen. How do we visualise and express what we do not know? The concept is explored in relation to climate change and our collective efforts to reduce anthropogenic greenhouse gas emissions. Our novel approach fosters dialogue and interactions between perspectives from economics and visual arts. The workshop creates a collaborative space, where those working with economics and/or visual arts come together to co-produce (and un-make) knowledge.

2. What's on the agenda?

The workshop brings together practices from economics and visual arts, often seen as two worlds that operate separately. Its working method is experimental, provocative, playful, and creative. There will be no traditional presentations. Instead there will be a mix of brief inputs from panelists, group discussions, and creative sessions, experimenting with artistic media, such as photography, collage and drawings. The provisional agenda includes:

- **09:45-10:15: Arrivals and refreshments**
- **10:15-10:35: Introductory plenary:** Welcome and aims/scope
- **10:35-11:15: Panelist keynotes:** Brief inputs from panelists, with visual stimuli, to inspire and provoke subsequent activities
- **11:15-11:55: Creative experimentation Part 1:** A series of facilitated arts-based activities (solo and group-based) guided by questions on uncertainty and the economics of climate change mitigation
- **11:55-12:40: Creative experimentation Part 2:** Foraging materials and making lumen prints to explore visualisations of uncertainty
- **12:40-13:20: Lunch**
- **13:20-14:00: Creative experimentation Part 3:** Reviewing creations from the first sessions and assembling/curating collective exhibit(s)
- **14:00-14:30: Final reflections:** Plenary session on ways forward

3. Are there any outputs expected from the workshop?

The workshop does not look for answers to specific questions, but rather seeks learning from the experience of integrating arts-science practices. We want to create space for participants to interact with people and practices they have not encountered before, and gain new perspectives on their work. There are no fixed expectations in terms of outputs from this workshop, which aspires to facilitate unexpected emergent insights and outcomes. However, we would like to eventually produce two outputs after the workshop (a booklet and exhibition, subject to funding). The timing for these is roughly up to one year after the date of the workshop.

4. Who is coming?

There will be up to 20 participants in total, including a core panel of economists and visual artists.

Core panel:

- **Richard Lewney** is a senior economist with over 40 years' experience in applied economic modelling and analysis to support public policymaking in the area of climate change, energy, environment, employment, regional & local development, and other topics of societal concern. Currently, he is Chair of the consultancy Cambridge Econometrics, and has been a Trustee of the Cambridge Trust for New Thinking in Economics since its founding in 2005. Richard obtained a Master's degree in Economics as a Fulbright Scholar at the University of Massachusetts at Amherst, USA. Further information on Richard's expertise can be found [here](#).
- **Hanne Peeraer** is an interdisciplinary artist and researcher working at the intersection of neuroaesthetics, perception, and meaning-making. With degrees from the Royal College of Art and the London Interdisciplinary School, her practice explores the psychological and cognitive underpinnings of illusion, using materials like light, glass, and paper to render complexity sensorially graspable. Her work has been exhibited internationally and engages with interdisciplinary collaborations on climate, cognition, and systems thinking. Further information can be found [here](#).
- **Serban Scriciu** is a senior research economist, policy shaper, and director and founder of [ICENS lab](#). He has around twenty years of research and policy experience in the area of climate change,

equity, and sustainability-related topics, having worked for both academia and (EU and international) policy institutions. When time permits, Şerban also pursues [photography](#). More is available on his [LinkedIn](#) and [UCL](#) profiles.

- [Duncan Wooldridge](#) is an artist and writer, with a focus on contemporary experimental photographic practices, photography in the future tense and photographic materialities. He is a Reader in Photography at the School of Digital Arts, Manchester Metropolitan University. He is the author of *To Be Determined: Photography and the Future* (SPBH/Mack, 2011) and co-editor of *The Routledge Companion to Global Photographies* (2025). He is the co-founder of the Global Photographies Network and the co-director of *object | multiple*, a platform for artists objects. Further information can be found [here](#).
- [Siân Macfarlane](#) is a Senior Lecturer in Photography at the School of Digital Arts, Manchester Metropolitan University. Her artistic practice spans historic material, photographic practice, performance, installation and film. Engagement with archival materials considers what is, and isn't, archived, and the historiographies of landscape. Work is currently concerned with literary and folkloric readings of post-industrial landscape, involving critical engagement with water legacies and energy futures. In this work she is involved in the Welsh Energy Humanities research group. Further information can be found [here](#).

Facilitators:

[Sarah Royston](#): Senior Research Fellow at the Global Sustainability Institute, Anglia Ruskin University

[James Norton](#): Narrative Arts Collective & Anglia Ruskin University

5. Who are the organisers?

The workshop is co-organised by LEAP lab and ICENS lab and is supported by the Centre for Research in the Arts, Social Sciences and Humanities (CRASSH) at the University of Cambridge.

[LEAP Lab](#) (Living Experiments in Arts-science Practice to re-imagine sustainability) is a transdisciplinary project involving a collective of researchers and practitioners at the University of Cambridge and Anglia Ruskin University. Its core question is: How can we go beyond existing forms of artistic and scientific practice, to imagine and create sustainable societies? LEAP Lab aims to create a space for being and re/researching together in multiple ways – scholarly, artistic, and beyond, to explore questions concerning sustainability.

[ICENS lab](#) (Interdisciplinary Climate Economics for Nature and Society) is a recently-established small social enterprise (community-interest company), registered in the UK that promotes diversity in economic thinking and arts-economics interactions. Its vision is of a world with a stabilised global climate system, an economy that cares for our planet and its inhabitants, and a society that considers, in its economic decision-making, ethics, equity, environmental quality, and wellbeing for all. In this world, the economics knowledge generation system places quantitative and qualitative findings, and rationality, morality and sentiment, on an equal footing. The power of narratives and storytelling, language and ordinary reasoning, visuals, values, aesthetics and arts in shaping economies is acknowledged alongside the typical classical logical thinking.